

HOZIRGI KUNDA JIZZAX VILOYATINING IJTIMOYIY-IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIDA BO‘LAJAK MUHANDIS-KONSTRUKTORLARINING KOMPETENSIYAVIY JIHATDAN ROLI

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ANNOTATSIYA Maqolada bo‘lajak muhandis-konstruktorlarining Jizzax viloyatini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishdagi o‘rniga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lib, ularni malakali etib yetishtirish usullari va yo‘nalishlari o‘rganilgan. Asosiy e‘tibor yosh mutaxassislar o‘rtasida texnik bilim, jamoada ishlash, kommunikativ ko‘nikmalar va qonunchilikni bilish kabi asosiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish zarurligiga qaratiladi. Ushbu maqsadga erishishning turli mexanizmlari va usullari, jumladan, ta‘lim dasturlarini yangilash, malaka oshirish, murabbiylik, amaliy tajriba va uzluksiz o‘rganish kabilar ko‘rib chiqiladi. Maqolada hududning muvaffaqiyatli ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishida muhandis-konstruktorlari malakasining muhimligi ta‘kidlangan va uni takomillashtirish yo‘llari taklif etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Qurilish muhandislari, kompetentsiya, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish, Jizzax viloyati, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi, ta‘lim dasturlari, malaka oshirish, amaliy tajriba.

ANNOTATION The article examines the role of future civil engineers in the socio-economic development of the Jizzakh region, and also studies the methods and directions of their training. The main focus is on the need to develop basic competencies in young specialists, such as technical knowledge, ability to work in a team, communication skills and knowledge of legislation. Various mechanisms and methods for achieving this goal are considered, including curriculum renewal, professional development, mentoring, field experience, and lifelong learning. The article emphasizes the importance of the qualifications of

civil engineers in the successful socio-economic development of the region and suggests ways to improve it.

Key words: Design engineer, competence, socio-economic development, Jizzakh region, Republic of Uzbekistan, educational programs, advanced training, practical experience.

KIRISH. Zamonaviy dunyoda hududlarni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda muhandis-konstruktorlarining roli tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Bu, ayniqsa, barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash va aholi turmush darajasini yuksaltirishda milliy iqtisodiyotning tarmoq va sohalari muhim o'rin tutadigan O'zbekiston kabi rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarga taalluqlidir. Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak muhandis-konstruktorlarining O'zbekiston Respublikasi Jizzax viloyatini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishdagi barkamol roli haqida so'z boradi.

Avvalo, Jizzax viloyatining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirish xususida to'xtaladigan bo'lsak, viloyat O'zbekistonning keyingi yillarda jadal rivojlanib borayotgan hududlaridan biridir. Viloyat sanoat, qishloq xo'jaligi va turizmni rivojlantirish uchun salmoqli salohiyatga ega. Viloyat hokimligi tomonidan sarmoya jalb etish, ishlab chiqarishni modernizatsiya qilish, yangi ish o'rinlari yaratish borasida izchil ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYASI. Keling endi ushbu salohiyatga xizmat qiluvchi hududni rivojlantirishda muhandis-konstruktorlarining o'rniga to'xtalaylik, ya'ni muhandis-konstruktorlar odamlar hayotini yaxshilash, iqtisodiy o'sish uchun shart-sharoit yaratuvchi infratuzilma loyihalarini amalga oshirishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Bu borada ayrim alarda berilishcha [Gapparov B.N., Makhmatkulov M.R. "Innovative approaches to improving the methodology of professional competence development of future builder-engineer constructors". Problems of architecture and construction (scientific and technical journal) Samarkand. 2023 year. Pages 243-244., Qosimov

J. A. et al. The role of software in the development of modeling in education //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2022. – Т. 2432. – №. 1., Qosimov J. A. et al. Development of methods for improving the lessons of information technology on the basis of graphic programs //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing, 2022. – Т. 2432. – №. 1. ,]o‘z fikr-mulohazalarini bildirishsa, boshqalari bu borada [Айнакулов М. А. Экономическая эффективность управления кластером в реальном секторе экономики // Экономика и социум. – 2022. – №. 2-1 (93). – С. 187-193., Махкамovich S. A. Iqtisodiyotni transformatsiyalash sharoitida klasterlar faoliyatini rivojlantirish bo‘yicha ba’zi tavsiyalar // International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 164-166., Abduhamidovich A. H., Baxriddinovich O.R.F., Parmanovich I.A. Mehnatni motivatsiyalashning maqbul tizimini loyihalashtirish tamoyillarini shakllantirish // Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 768-774., Abduvalievich M. A. Xo‘jalik yuritishni transformatsiyalash negizida xo‘jalik yuritish klasterlarining nazariy asoslari // International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 356-359.] berilsa, boshqa manbalarda esa bu yo‘nalishda boshqacha fikrlar bildirilgan [Ne'matillaevich G. B., son M. A. A., son A. B. T. Directions of agrocluster based on cooperation in the economy // Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. - 2021. - Т. 1. – no. 5. - S. 780-785., Burkhanovich M. A. Digital economy-product quality-control-professional competence // International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. - 2022. - S. 162-164., Parmanovich I. A., Mahkamovich S. A. Methods, Perspectives and Mechanisms of Increasing the Efficiency of Tourism in Jizakh Region //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2021. – С. 558-563.]. Albatta o‘z navbatida, ular yo‘llar, ko‘priklar, turar-joy va sanoat binolari, suv ta’minoti va kanalizatsiya tizimlarini qurishda ishtirok etadi.

Shunday ekan, bo'lajak muhandis-konstruktorlarining malaka va ko'nikmalari quyidagi me'yor doirasida bo'lishi talab qilinadi, ya'ni Jizzax viloyatini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda samarali ishtirok etish uchun bo'lajak muhandis-konstruktorlar bir qator asosiy kompetensiyalarga ega bo'lishi kerak:

1. Texnik bilim va ko'nikmalar: Bo'lajak muhandis-konstruktorlar milliy iqtisodiyotda ishlatiladigan zamonaviy texnologiyalar va materiallarni yaxshi tushunishlari kerak;

2. Jamoada ishlash qobiliyati: Ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish loyihalari odatda katta jamoalar, jumladan, turli fanlar vakillari tomonidan amalga oshiriladi. Samarali jamoaviy ish loyiha muvaffaqiyatining kalitidir;

3. Aloqa ko'nikmalari: Bo'lajak muhandis-konstruktorlar mijozlar, pudratchilar va ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish jarayonining boshqa ishtirokchilari bilan muloqot qila olishlari kerak.

4. Qonunchilikni bilish: Muhandis-konstruktorlar ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish jarayonini tartibga soluvchi huquqiy-me'yoriy hujjatlarni bilishlari kerak;

5. Muammoni hal qilish qobiliyati: Ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish jarayonida tez va samarali yechimlarni talab qiladigan turli muammolar ko'pincha paydo bo'ladiki, ularni tezda yumshatish ko'nukmasiga ega bo'lishlari kerak.

NATIJARLAR. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Jizzax viloyatini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirish sharoitida bo'lajak muhandis-konstruktorlarning malakasini tatbiq etish va oshirish uchun tayyorlash va malakasini oshirishning turli mexanizm va usullaridan foydalanish mumkin. Keling, ulardan ba'zilarini ko'rib chiqaylik:

1. Ta'lim dasturlari:

Ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish loyihalarni boshqarish va boshqa muhim strategic yo'nalishlar bo'yicha joriy kurslar va modullarni o'z ichiga olgan

zamonaviy ta'lim dasturlarini ishlab chiqish va amalga oshirish. Jumladan, tajribali mutaxassislardan amaliy mashg'ulotlar, amaliyot va mahorat darslarini tinglash.

2. Malaka oshirish va qayta tayyorlash:

Bo'lajak muhandis-konstruktorlar uchun muntazam ravishda malaka oshirish kurslarini tashkil etish. Ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida yangi talablar va standartlarni hisobga olgan holda mutaxassislarni qayta tayyorlash dasturlarini o'tash.

3. Mentorlik va murabbiylik:

Tajribali muhandis-konstruktorlari o'z tajriba va bilimlarini yosh mutaxassislar bilan baham ko'radigan murabbiylik tizimini yaratish. Ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida ilg'or tajriba almashish uchun tarmoq uchrashuvlari va tadbirlarni tashkil etish.

4. Amaliy tajriba:

Talabalar va yosh mutaxassislarga tajribali muhandis-konstruktorlar rahbarligida haqiqiy ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish loyihalarida ishtirok etish imkoniyatini berish. Ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish sohasidagi dolzarb muammolarni hal qilish uchun tanlovlar tashkil etish.

5. Uzluksiz ta'lim va o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash:

Bo'lajak muhandis-konstruktorlar o'rtasida uzluksiz o'rganish va o'z-o'zini takomillashtirish madaniyatini rivojlantirish. Texnikaviy yoki tegishli fanlar bo'yicha elektron ta'lim resurslariga, vebinarlarga va onlayn kurslarga kirishni ta'minlash.

6. Yangi texnologiyalar va vositalardan foydalanish:

MUHOKAMA. Ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatish startegik dasturlarini loyihalash, modellashtirish va boshqarish uchun zamonaviy texnologiyalar va dasturiy ta'minotni joriy etish. Muhandis-konstruktorlarni yangi vositalar va texnologiyalar bilan ishlashga o'rgatish, shu orqali ularning mehnat bozorida raqobatbardoshligini oshirish.

Ushbu va boshqa ko‘plab mexanizmlar va usullar bo‘lajak muhandis-konstruktorlarining malakasini oshirishga, ularning kasbiy kompetentligini oshirishga va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishga hissa qo‘shish samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi.

XULOSA. Xulosa o‘rnida shuni qayd etish mumkinki, yetuk va malakali muhandis-konstruktorlar O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Jizzax viloyatini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda muhim o‘rin tutadi. Ular infratuzilma loyihalarini amalga oshirishda ishtirok etib, yangi ish o‘rinlari yaratib, aholi turmush darajasini oshirishga ko‘maklashadi. Bu sohada muvaffaqiyatli ishlash uchun bo‘lajak muhandis-konstruktorlar doimiy ravishda o‘z bilim va ko‘nikmalarini oshirib borishlari, muloqot ko‘nikmalarini va jamoada ishlash ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishlari zarur.

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